

Qualitative Study of Organizational Management Challenges and Strategies Himpunan Mahasiswa Islam (HMI) at STIE Ganesha

Putri Khailla Dwi Utami^{1✉}, Aep Saefullah²

putrikhailladwiutami09@gmail.com¹, aep@stieganessa.ac.id²

¹² Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia, Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi Ganesha Jakarta, Indonesia

<p>Keywords: Islamic Student Association, Organizational Management, Organizational Challenges, Strategy Management, STIE Ganesha</p>	<h3>Abstract</h3>
<p>Submitted: 19/07/2025</p>	<p>This research aims to identify the challenges and management strategies of the Islamic Student Association (HMI) in the STIE Ganesha environment through a qualitative approach. Data were collected through in-depth interviews, participatory observations, and documentation studies with HMI members and administrators and related parties at STIE Ganesha. The results of the study show that the main challenges in HMI management include limited human resources, low member participation, and obstacles in communication and coordination between members. This research emphasizes the importance of adaptive and participatory management strategies to improve the performance and sustainability of HMI in the academic environment. The implication is the need for institutional support as well as member capacity building as the foundation of effective organizational management.</p>
<p>Revised: 27/07/2025</p>	
<p>Accepted: 28/07/2025</p>	
<p>Author Correspondent: Putri Khailla Dwi Utami Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia, Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi Ganesha Jakarta, Indonesia Jl. Legoso Raya No.31, Pisangan, Kec. Ciputat Timur., Kota Tangerang Selatan, Banten 15419 putrikhailladwiutami09@gmail.com</p>	

INTRODUCTION

Student organizations are one of the important forums for students to develop their potential and improve the quality of leadership and organizational skills. In higher education, student organizations not only function as a gathering place for students, but also as a medium to channel aspirations, strengthen solidarity, and build character and managerial skills. One of the student organizations that has a strategic role at the university level is the Islamic Student Association (HMI).

The Islamic Student Association is an organization established to accommodate and nurture Muslim students so that they can contribute positively in various aspects of life, both in the academic, social, and religious fields. In the STIE Ganesha environment, the existence of HMI has a significant influence in shaping character and increasing student involvement in productive and useful organizational activities. However, in carrying out its role, HMI at STIE Ganesha faces various challenges that affect the effectiveness of the organization's management (Darisman Solin 2018).

The challenges faced come not only from internal factors such as limited human resources, lack of motivation of members, and obstacles in communication, but also from external aspects such as changes in social dynamics and the need to adapt to technological developments (Kusumaningrum et al. 2025). Therefore, an appropriate and effective management strategy is needed so that HMI at STIE Ganesha is able to carry out its functions and responsibilities optimally.

This research uses a qualitative approach to in-depth examine the various challenges faced by HMI and the management strategies implemented by the organization within the scope of the STIE Ganesha campus. By understanding the existing problems and solutions, it is hoped that this research can contribute to the development of a better student organization and become a reference for HMI administrators and related parties in improving organizational performance.

Literature Review

The Concept of Organizational Management in the Islamic Student Association (HMI)

Organizational management in HMI is based on Islamic values that prioritize the principles of deliberation, justice, and trust in every decision-making. HMI management adopts a collegial collective system to maintain the alignment of the organization's vision and mission and ensure the active participation of all members in every decision-making process. This is in accordance with the basic principles of leadership in Islam which emphasizes deliberation as a way to achieve the best decisions for the common good (Abdurrahim 2023).

Principles of Islamic Value-Based Organizational Management

Management in HMI integrates basic Islamic values such as monotheism, deliberation (*syuura*), benefit (*mashlahah*), justice (*adl*), and responsibility (*mas'uliyah*). These values are the moral and ethical foundation in running an organization, so every policy and action of the organization must reflect these values. For example, fairness in resource management and leaders' responsibility for decisions are real implementations of Islamic values in the management of HMI.

Cadre Management and Development Strategy in HMI

One of the main strategies in HMI management is to strengthen cadre regeneration through systematic and continuous training to produce competent leaders with integrity. This basic cadre training applies the classic management function, namely planning, organizing, implementing, and supervising so that every cadre activity can run effectively and produce good cadre quality. In addition, continuous member capacity development is important so that the organization remains adaptive and relevant to the times and technology (Sinaga et al. 2025).

Challenges in HMI Organization Management

HMI faces various challenges, both from internal and external factors. Inside, the challenges are in the form of limited human resources, low motivation and participation of members, and communication and coordination obstacles between members. On the other hand, social developments and digital technologies demand that HMIs adapt quickly to address the gap between organizational idealism and real practice on the

ground. This challenge must be answered with management innovation and organizational strengthening, including digitalization (Habibani and Frinaldi 2025).

Peran Manajemen Organisasi dalam Membentuk Karakter Mahasiswa

Effective organizational management also plays a role in the formation of member characters, such as honesty, hard work, creativity, communicative, and responsible (Hasanah 2023). The process of preparing a structured work program through management functions (planning, organizing, implementing, supervising) provides space for the formation of this character systematically in student organizations, including HMI. Thus, organizational management not only manages activities, but also shapes the quality of the human resources involved.

Organizational Management as the Key to Sustainability and the Relevance of HMI

The importance of organizational management in ensuring the sustainability and relevance of HMI is shown in the attention to transparency, accountability, and strengthening solidarity and collaboration between members and with external elements. The "HMI Back to Value" movement, for example, re-emphasizes the basic values of the organization and strengthens Islamic value-based management to maintain the existence and competitiveness of HMI as a progressive student organization.

RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses a qualitative method with a case study approach to understand in depth the challenges and management strategies of the Islamic Student Association (HMI) within STIE Ganesha. This method was chosen because it allows researchers to explore phenomena naturally and contextually, so that they can comprehensively understand the perspectives of the members and administrators.

Subject and Data Collection

The research subjects consist of administrators and members of HMI who are purposively selected because they are considered competent and have relevant information. The research location is centered on the STIE Ganesha campus environment. Data was collected through three main techniques: in-depth interviews with open-ended questions to explore respondents' experiences and views; participatory observation in which the researcher is directly involved in organizational activities such as meetings and internal/external activities; as well as documentation studies from activity reports, minutes, and other organizational documents to complete the data.

Data Analysis and Validity

The collected data was analyzed qualitatively with an interactive approach, including the stages of reduction, presentation, and conclusion drawn. The role of the researcher is very important as the main instrument that observes, collects, and analyzes data directly, so that objectivity is maintained. To ensure the validity of the data, this study uses source triangulation (comparing data from administrators and members) and triangulation techniques (comparing data from interviews, observations, and documentation). In addition, member checks were also carried out to verify provisional findings with informants. This method is designed to provide a comprehensive and in-depth overview of HMI management at STIE Ganesha.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Results

Based on the results of in-depth interviews, participatory observations, and documentation studies conducted on the management and members of the Islamic

Student Association (HMI) within STIE Ganesha, a concrete picture was obtained of the challenges faced and the strategies used in the management of the organization.

Internal Organizational Challenges

The informants revealed several internal challenges, such as the limitation of competent and committed human resources in organizational management. Not all members actively participate in organizational activities, thus hindering the implementation of work programs. In addition, communication between members and administrators sometimes does not run effectively, which causes coordination to be less optimal in the implementation of daily activities. (Hidayat 2024)

External Organizational Challenges

Challenges from outside the organization are also quite significant, including changes in social dynamics and technological developments that require organizations to be able to adapt quickly (Ani et al. 2024). The management feels that digital transformation in the management of activities and communication has not been fully optimal, so there is a possibility of information gaps among members.

Organizational Management Strategy

To overcome these challenges, HMI STIE Ganesha implements several effective management strategies. The first strategy is to increase the capacity of administrators through structured training and coaching so that administrators can carry out their duties more professionally and with integrity (Nufuz et al. 2025). This training includes the development of leadership skills, time management, and organizational administrative management techniques.

The second strategy is to strengthen internal communication by utilizing information technology such as WhatsApp groups, social media, and other communication applications to speed up and facilitate coordination between members and management. This strategy has been proven to increase member participation and awareness in following the organization's agenda.

The third strategy is to strengthen regeneration through consistent and sustainable programs. Cadre regeneration is carried out systematically so that the regeneration of the management is always maintained and the number of competent cadres can continue to grow. This approach ensures the long-term sustainability of the organization.

Table 1. Table Illustration: Challenges and Management Strategies of HMI STIE Ganesha

Aspects	Key Challenges	Management Strategy
Internal	Limited competent and committed human resources	Structured management training and coaching
	Low member participation	Strengthening communication through digital technology
	Less effective communication	Strengthening consistent and sustainable cadre regeneration
External	Rapid social and technological change	Adaptation to the use of information technology
	Digital transformation is not optimal	Improve information dissemination and coordination

Structure Explanation:

This structure shows the division of challenges into two main groups, namely internal and external challenges faced by HMI at STIE Ganesha. In the internal aspect,

the main problem is the limited capacity of members and administrators and the lack of participation and effective communication (Miran et al. 2024). Therefore, the strategy implemented focuses on coaching administrators through continuous training, strengthening digital communication, and systematically developing cadres so that the organization has reliable human resources and high commitment.

On the external aspect, the challenge comes from the need for organizations to continue to adapt to social changes and rapid technological advances (Yanti et al. 2024). HMI has not fully succeeded in carrying out maximum digital transformation, resulting in an information gap between members. To respond to this, the strategy is to optimize the use of digital technology so that communication and information dissemination become faster and more efficient.

With this evaluation structure, HMI can clearly map problems and assess how effective the strategies are in overcoming these challenges, so that the organization can continue to develop and be relevant to the times.

Discussion

The results of this study provide an overview that the main challenge of HMI management within STIE Ganesha is closely related to the issue of human resources and internal communication that is not optimal. This is in line with organizational management theory which explains the importance of the role of competent human resources and effective coordination in the success of the organization.

The challenges of HR management and member participation reflect a lack of motivation and active involvement in the organization, which in the context of HMI is very important because the organization is based on Islamic values that demand commitment and solidarity among members. Therefore, management training and capacity building is a very relevant strategic step in improving the quality of leadership and organizational management (Kamala et al. 2025).

The use of digital communication technology shows the adaptation of the organization to the times and is an effective solution in overcoming communication barriers (Sasmita et al. 2025). Technology helps accelerate the dissemination of information and facilitate the coordination of activities, so that the actualization needs of members are met and organizational programs can run more smoothly.

Strengthening cadre regeneration is also the main strategy so that the organization can continue to regenerate leadership in a sustainable manner (Miftah 2025). This is in accordance with the principles of organizational management which emphasizes the importance of developing human resources as the main capital of the organization. With good regeneration, HMI is able to maintain its existence in the campus environment and become a forum for developing the potential of students who have a leadership spirit and strong Islamic values.

Overall, the results and management strategies of HMI at STIE Ganesha confirm that adaptive organizational management, communicative, and oriented towards cadre development is the key to the success and sustainability of the organization. This research shows that the synergy between Islamic values and modern management principles can increase the effectiveness of student organization management in the university environment.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

In general, this study found that the management of HMI organizations within STIE Ganesha applies the principle of collegial collective in the decision-making process. This means that decisions are taken jointly through deliberation, based on Islamic values

such as justice, trust, and honesty so that each member feels that they have a shared role and responsibility in the organization.

However, in practice, organizations face a number of major challenges. The main challenge is the lack of involvement of members after they have attended cadre training. There is a gap between the idealism carried during the training and the reality of the spirit of members' contributions in the field, so that the sustainability of the organization's programs is sometimes hampered. In addition, social developments and advances in digital technology force HMI to adapt and continue to innovate so that it remains relevant among today's students.

This research also emphasizes the importance of strengthening regeneration as the heart of the organization, innovation in the use of technology to support organizational activities, and the consistent implementation of Islamic values in all activities. With these steps, HMI is expected to maintain its existence, and even become a student organization that is increasingly progressive, relevant, and has a wide impact on the campus environment and society.

In conclusion, if HMI wants to remain solid and develop, they must continue to strengthen the cadre system, be open to technological innovation, and always practice Islamic values in real actions, not just slogans. That way, HMI can become a role model for student organizations that are adaptive, progressive, and ready to face the challenges of the times.

Suggestion

Based on the results of research on management challenges and strategies

The organization of the Islamic Student Association (HMI) within STIE Ganesha, is very important for this organization to strengthen the regeneration in a sustainable manner. Cadre regeneration activities should not only stop at initial training, but must be a continuous and structured process so that they can produce cadres who not only understand the values of leadership and organizational management, but are also able to internalize Islamic values deeply.

In addition, in facing the digital era which has become an inseparable part of student life, HMI needs to optimize the use of digital technology. The use of social media platforms, organizational applications, and other digital communication methods must be maximized to facilitate coordination between members and increase their active participation in organizational activities. This will greatly help organizations in maintaining effective and responsive communication.

An equally important condition is to build a culture of active and consistent participation from all members. Organizations need to create an atmosphere that supports the involvement of each member by providing clear accountability and appreciating the contributions they make. Thus, the spirit and commitment of members to continue to participate in every program and activity can be well maintained.

The practical practice of Islamic values must also be the main foundation in every aspect of HMI management and activities. By upholding the principles of justice, trust, and honesty, the organization not only becomes structurally strong, but also able to build trust and integrity in the eyes of its members and the campus community.

Finally, organizations must remain sensitive to ongoing social changes. A quick and innovative response to various developments, both in social and technological aspects, will maintain the relevance of HMI for increasingly dynamic students. Innovation in work programs and management strategies must always be pursued so that HMI is able to adapt and continue to make a positive contribution to the campus and the wider community. By implementing these things, it is hoped that HMI within STIE Ganesha can be more advanced and effective in carrying out its role as a student organization.

REFERENCE

- Abdurrahim, Abdurrahim. 2023. "PRINSIP PERMUSYAWARATAN DALAM ISLAM DIKAITKAN DENGAN HIKMAT KEBIJAKSANAAN DALAM PERMUSYAWARATAN PERWAKILAN." Doctoral, Universitas Hasanuddin. <https://repository.unhas.ac.id/id/eprint/24446/>.
- Ani, Nyree, Rifqa Nabila Muti, and Lista Meria. 2024. "Strategi Efektif Menghadapi Dinamika Global: Pendekatan Manajemen Perubahan Organisasi yang Terbukti." *ADI Bisnis Digital Interdisiplin Jurnal* 5 (2): 56–63. <https://doi.org/10.34306/abdi.v5i2.1174>.
- Darisman Solin, 140305003. 2018. "Tingkat Prestasi Mahasiswa Yang Mengikuti Organisasi HMI (Studi Kasus Pada Fuf Dan Tarbiyah UIN Ar- Raniry)." Skripsi, UIN Ar-Raniry Banda Aceh. <http://library.ar-raniry.ac.id>.
- Habibani, Rhaysya Admami, and Aldri Frinaldi. 2025. "INOVASI BUDAYA ORGANISASI PUBLIK DALAM ERA DIGITAL: PELUANG DAN STRATEGI IMPLEMENTASI." *SOCIAL : Jurnal Inovasi Pendidikan IPS* 5 (2): 2. <https://doi.org/10.51878/social.v5i2.5365>.
- Hasanah, Zulfa. 2023. "Manajemen Organisasi dalam Membentuk Karakter di Himpunan Mahasiswa Program Studi Manajemen Pendidikan Fakultas Ilmu Tarbiyah dan Keguruan UIN Syarif Hidayatullah Jakarta Periode 2019/2021." bachelorThesis, Jakarta : FITK UIN Syarif Hidayatullah Jakarta. <https://repository.uinjkt.ac.id/dspace/handle/123456789/76346>.
- Hidayat, Rahmat. 2024. "Peran Komunikasi Organisasi Dalam Meningkatkan Kinerja Pengurus Desa Dahian Tambuk Kecamatan Mihing Raya Kabupaten Gunung Mas Provinsi Kalimantan Tengah: The Role of Organizational Communication in Improving the Performance of Village Officials in Dahian Tambuk, Mihing Raya District, Gunung Mas Regency, Central Kalimantan Province." *Pencerah Publik* 11 (1): 1. <https://doi.org/10.33084/pencerah.v11i1.9749>.
- Kamala, Jum'iyatul, Selvi Aulya Salsa, Nurilawati Nurilawati, Raja Muhammad Iqbal Fachriansyah, and Firman Firman. 2025. "Integrasi Pelatihan Dan Pengembangan SDM Dalam Meningkatkan Kapasitas Organisasi." *EDU SOCIATA (JURNAL PENDIDIKAN SOSIOLOGI)* 8 (1): 1. <https://doi.org/10.33627/es.v8i1.3307>.
- Kasmawanto, Zuli, and Khoirotnun Ni'mah. 2025. "MANAJEMEN KONFLIK UNTUK KEBERHASILAN ORGANISASI: STRATEGI DAN TANTANGAN." *HUMANIS: Jurnal Ilmu-Ilmu Sosial Dan Humaniora* 17 (1): 1. <https://doi.org/10.52166/humanis.v17i01.8761>.
- Kusumaningrum, Hesti, Annisa Esa Nurrohimah, Rintika Putri Pratama, and Ahamad Bayhaqi Algifaro. 2025. "Strategi Strategi Menghadapi Tantangan Lingkungan Eksternal Dalam Dunia Pendidikan." *Jurnal Manajemen Dan Pendidikan Agama Islam* 3 (1): 286–95. <https://doi.org/10.61132/jmpai.v3i1.864>.
- Miftah, Dede. 2025. "Sistem Kaderisasi Nahdlatul Ulama Dalam Upaya Meningkatkan Efektiviti Organisasi: Studi Deskriptif Di PWNU Provinsi Jawa Barat." Other, UIN Sunan Gunung Djati Bandung. <https://doi.org/10/Lampiran.pdf>.
- Miran, Ika, Stefani Chandra, Suyono Suyono, et al. 2024. "Peningkatan Kapasitas Pengurus Organisasi: Memperkuat Sinergi, Menyalakan Inovasi Dan Menggapai Prestasi." *JUDIKAT: Jurnal Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat* 4 (2): 2. <https://doi.org/10.35145/judikat.v4i2.4873>.
- Nufuz, Devi Alhayatun, Muhammad Hadyanshah Mahendra, Abdullah Faqih, and Nurul Setianingrum. 2025. "Strategi Efektif Dalam Manajemen Perubahan: Membangun Ketahanan Organisasi Di Era Digital." *Menulis: Jurnal Penelitian Nusantara* 1 (6): 6. <https://doi.org/10.59435/menulis.v1i6.388>.
- Sasmita, Fadilla Aliffia, Rizki Nur Hafida, Alya Zhafira, and Syahbana. 2025. "Analisis Peran

- Media Digital Dalam Meningkatkan Efektivitas Komunikasi Organisasi Ikatan Mahasiswa Muhammadiyah Di Tengah Tantangan Disrupsi Digital." *KESKAP: Jurnal Kesejahteraan Sosial, Komunikasi Dan Administrasi Publik* 4 (2): 2. <https://doi.org/10.30596/keskap.v4i2.26111>.
- Sinaga, Crisdayanti Sinaga, Dina Claudia Purba, Salsabilla Putri Lisari, and Nazwa Feryal Kamila. 2025. "Dinamika Pengembangan Kapasitas Organisasi Dalam Menghadapi Tantangan Globalisasi." *EDU SOCIATA (JURNAL PENDIDIKAN SOSIOLOGI)* 8 (1): 1. <https://doi.org/10.33627/es.v8i1.3258>.
- Yanti, Novi, Sania Oktavia Nasution, Winda Khofifah, Yulia Hidayat, and Ahmad Mukhlisin. 2024. "Tantangan Masa Depan : Adaptasi Anatomi Organisasi Di Era Digital." *Jurnal Teknologi Pendidikan Dan Pembelajaran | E-ISSN : 3026-6629* 2 (1): 1.